

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- II May - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

The Politics of Electoral Promises and its Effect on Voting Behavior

Paper Id : 20168 Submission Date : 2025-05-19 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16451459

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Priyanka Kumari

Researcher
Political Science
Vinoba Bhave University
Hazaribagh, Jharkhand,
India

Abstract

Voting process in India reflects the heart of its democracy and its evolving nature over the period. Post independence successive governments have nurtured and uplifted the poor and vulnerable populations by providing them with material goods such as rice, wheat, salt etc. This socio- economic enhancement of people in need was necessary back then but nowadays political parties are offering absurd and illogical promises just before elections.

Each year there is election in any of the states of the country making the economic health susceptible to mismanagement by false & illogical pre poll promises. From giving electronic gadgets to transferring a certain amount of money in voter's accounts to irrational talk of changing reservation policy.

Recently Supreme court of India issued a notice to the center & ECI (Election commission of India) hearing a plea against the pre poll promises usually freebies. ECI said it has no power to regulate or take action against the parties making promises & freebies. ECI cited DPSP of the constitution of India that says state shall endeavor to frame various welfare schemes for better livelihood of its citizens.

When custodians start distributing with negative growth budget welfare schemes, the cost of living goes up and puts more people in poverty than pulling them up from it. These large chunks of money can be utilized in so many basic infrastructure developments but this so called "welfare schemes" supersedes the actual work at the cost of taxpayers. So, it is imperative to build a political consensus involving the center as well as states in concurrence with the ECI to address the misuse of welfare schemes and the resultant adverse impacts on the country's fiscal health. This paper explores whether the electoral promises really attract voters that are targeted by different political parties and also try to trace if the promised schemes ever be fulfilled by respective governments.

Keywords Electoral Promises, Voting Behavior, Democracy, Election Commission, Party Politics, Freebies, Mobilization, Rewari Culture, Election Manifesto, Public Opinion, Political Culture

Introduction

India being democratic set up with universal adult suffrage elects its legislators for a fixed term basis. This practice involves whole of nation in national (Lok Sabha Election) and State assembly elections carried out by the Election Commission of India (ECI). ECI regulates the election procedure and make changes in rules People choose to vote for the party they believe will perform well and make people centric policies for a better future. Political parties came up with manifestoes full with their ideologies and schemes to woo voters.

In recent years many political parties whether they are national or state, are publishing their manifestos which contains foreign policy, economic policy etc. other than its basic ideology if they come to power. Welfare schemes are good for social and economic upliftment of people in need viz. pension schemes for aged and helpless, affordable quality

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- II May - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

education for all, agricultural loan waiving etc. But nowadays, a new trend has been started by some political parties by directly promising absurd and illogical schemes which can be commonly called as 'freebies'. Free power, free grains and a basic income to everybody are becoming a norm. Since this term freebies is not so old and therefore it is quite difficult for the authors and political commentators to differentiate between welfare schemes and freebies [1]. And it is so, because the constitution of India itself mentions India as a welfare state.

Elections in democracies play significant role in changing the fate of the nation. People exercise their power to choose their representatives. Political parties present their policies during election campaigns and influence voters to support their party. Freebies are offered as a part of political campaigns to attract voters. Promises are promises met by political parties on they will provide the public for free if they win the election. Political parties offer free gas electricity scooters by cycle laptop with the Internet free bus tickets phones and even a mixer grinder.

Objective of study

The main aim of the study of the paper is to thoroughly and comprehensively figure out the feasibility and affordability of the so-called popular welfare schemes that are promised while high voltage political campaign. This paper includes the data and facts of promises in reference to their social and economic impact impartially. This article talks about promises and their usage during election. A brief history of the distribution of freebies has been mentioned with a proper analysis and at the same time insights have been given about the current situation that has been taking place in last couple of years with suitable examples. This article scrutinizes the role that irrational and illegal promises play in the development and demotion of society. The paper aims to explore the complex interplay between electoral politics, social welfare, and fiscal responsibility in India.

The objective of this paper is also to find out the impact of all these combined symbolic action plans on the voting behavior especially of women voters. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to highlight the fact that what impact does it have on the voters in case of fulfillment or non - fulfillment of basic amenities of the common people. It mentions the remark of the honorable Supreme Court of India on this matter either through Suo-Motto or through PIL. The article finally concludes with the notion that irrational freebies immediately before the elections enrich on the legal right of the people to free and fair election.

Review of Literature

N K Singh of 15th finance commission warned that freebies are a quick passport to fiscal disaster. In July 2022, PM Narendra Modi too in a public meeting highlighted the freebie culture and said that "attempts are being made to collect votes by distributing free "Rewaris". Rewari is a Gujarati sweet which is distributed by frauds to make friends evade Taxes. Besides this several NGOs and intellectuals also criticized this freebie culture. Free and fair election is the principal feature of a democracy [2]. A free and fair election expresses the will of the people by choosing the representative of their choice. The primary feature of a free and fair election is that everyone has the right to cast their vote for the candidate or party of their choice without intimidation or fear. Freebies announced by politicians prior to the elections have a tendency to influence voter's opinions. This indirect influence affects the idea of free and fair elections. Some considered this practice as bribing the public for their votes in exchange for benefits.

On this topic, Several studies have been done by many authors, intellectuals and institution in which some are considered for review for this research paper such as Election Commission of India's (ECI 24th April 2015) instructions to political parties in manifestos, Subramanian Balaji S (2013) Government of Tami Nadu, Supreme court (2022) "freebies and welfare schemes are different things", Mathur Anisa (August 2022) "poll promises part of free speech: app in Supreme Court in Freebies case, Pradhan Mantri Modi Narendra (2022) "rewari culture dangerous, must end: PM Modi slams politics of Freebies", Fiscal responsible and Budget Management Act (2003), Singh Charan (2017) "A review of the FRBM act", Paani Narendra and Virginius (2007) "freebies in Indian politics: A critical analysis".

This paper explores the reasons why political parties use freebies as an electoral strategy. There are several reasons here like vote bank consolidation, competitive populism, emotional connect, addressing immediate concerns, mobilization and turn out perception of good governance etc. Freebies in politics have a strong psychological and emotional appeal to voters, tapping into various psychological factors that influence human behavior. Freebies are often used as a tool for vote bank politics which refers to the strategy of forgetting a specific voters groups or communities to secure their support. When voters receive freebies, they may develop a sense of gratitude and indebtedness towards the party providing those benefits. This emotional connection can lead to a long term association with the party and tendency to vote for them in subsequent elections.

In conclusion the literature on the politics of electoral promises and its effect on voting behavior present an analytical approach in various parts. By evaluating these works, Future research can build on this foundation to gain a more comprehensive understanding about the political promises and its effect [3].

Main Text

From 1952 onwards, the political parties used to publish their intent & ideologies through manifestos. Popular trends and promises were common among leaders while addressing public meetings. From Indira Gandhi's 'Garibi Hatao' and Janata Dal's 'Save Democracy' & 'Save constitution' to Narendra Modi's 'Sabka Sath Sabka Vikas' & of course the popular promises of materialistic gifts for voters, we have come a long way [4]. In recent years it is seen that freebies are promised by political parties on the ground of winning election.

It is true that in India the poor, illiterate and underprivileged people vote in larger proportion as compared to the rich and privileged ones. This is certainly true in case of local self-government elections. There can be many reasons behind this but we can't deny the fact of cash or liquor for votes. Many pre-poll statements to woo the voters also plays important role. Electoral promises or sometimes freebies are like a double edged sword which is becoming more and more dangerous with each and every passing electoral practice. With the commencement of every election season, political parties across the country promise a whole bucket of list full with full of promises in lieu of votes in favor [5].

Factors Governing Alluring Promises

Demographic division plays an important role in shaping electoral perception for political parties. Having over 65% of its population under the age of 35, India has a large youth population. Keeping in mind, the political parties grab the nerves of this large chunk of youth. They know the scientific temperament and wisdom of Indian youth. So they came up with a bucket of schemes such as distributing electronic gadgets like mobile, laptops etc. sometimes with monthly installment of few pennies for unemployed youth.

Women population in India contributes very less in workforce and hence is dependent on their male partner or on family for their personal expenses. Attracting them by promising alluring schemes and services is easy for the parties participating in election. This large chunk of population easily gets carried away by the captivating promises for domestic equipment. Considering the higher participation of women in elections many welfare schemes have been launched from time to time for the self - reliance of women like Mudra loans, Pradhan Mantri Matri Vandana Yojana, Sukanya Samriddhi Yojna, Pragati scholarship for girls, Mahila Sakthi Kendra etc. by the central government which is very good step but, when apart from these schemes, the government focuses more on economic incentives rather than employment, then this becomes a lesson in freebies, instead of being for the welfare of the people. For example free or subsidized goods and services range from Amma's canteens in Tamil Nadu & Nitish Kumar's bicycle in Bihar to items such as color tv, cell phones, mixer grinders, laptops, Buffaloes, cows, mangal sutras for the brides and several other gifts [6] .

Regionalism is an important yet less talked controversial topic which if not handled carefully can harm and destroy the social structure and integration of any country. The rise of regionalism in the last couple of years is on surge especially after the rise in social media trends. For example, issue of mother tongue in the states of Southern India especially in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Maharashtra. Number of cases of beating and lay off of people migrated from north India has been recorded for not speaking the local language. This type of hooliganism is created by the local party workers to consolidate the native voters and gain popular votes. Another pre-poll promise of reservation in private jobs is also trending in several state elections. With an eye on exploiting voter's anger and swaying in favor, opposition parties came with the promise of reservation in private jobs. Making such promises indicates indulging in triggering emotive subjects by sugarcoating them as real issues if taken seriously; it would lead to unnecessary animosity among states. This is so because no state can claim that people their employed in that state only, it is certain that in search of jobs & better opportunity people migrate.

Legal Interventions

The question of intervention lies in the fact that whether court can assess and give decision regarding the viability and legality of pre poll promises or not. Article 282 of the Indian Constitution grants both the central and the state governments the authority to

allocate resources for any public purpose, even if it falls outside the ambit of parliament or the state legislature. The significant case in the honorable Supreme Court in Subramanian Balaji vs Govt of Tamil Nadu (2013) has directed the Election Commission of India to issue guidelines on the election manifesto to be included as a part of the Modal Code of Conduct [7]. The Supreme Court said that the freebies in the election manifesto influence the minds of people and creates a bias in them. It destroys the root of free, fair and partial election. However, the Supreme Court refused to intervene in this matter citing part IV (DPSP) of constitution of India. The Supreme Court stated that political parties distributing different gifts item to deserving people is directly related to welfare of people and this is what enshrined in our constitution. A practicing advocate and close ally of the ruling BJP government Mr. Ashwini Kumar Upadhyay filed a petition in the Supreme Court in 2022 arguing freebie promises as bribery to voters [8]. He quoted the then IPC 1860, section 171B of bribery and section 171C of undue influence. He also mentioned that using the hard earned tax payer's money as freebies do not serve a public purpose and violates the constitution of India.

Another important act to curb unethical practices in election is Representation of People Act, 1951. The Section 123(1) of this act explicitly prohibits bribery during elections. It highlights that offering a gift, offer or promise with the intention of swaying a voter's decision can be classified as bribery [9]. But a serious drawback of this act is, it emphasis actions on individual candidate or their agents and not on the party to which he/she may belong in case of any accountability of violation of Modal Code of Conduct.

Impact of Freebies on Voters During Election

According to Milton Friedman, Nobel Laureate "There is no such thing as a free lunch, everything has to be paid for with taxes, if not today or tomorrow, then the next day because someone has to pay for the freebies. The poor pay for the gifts, not the rich, because the government collects taxes on everything" [10].

The high cost of freebies and subsidies has an additional impact on the GDP of states-

State (Election Date)	Estimated cost (Rs. Billion)	%of GDP
Maharashtra (Nov-Dec 2024)	960	2.2
Karnataka (May 2023)	537	1.9
Telangana (Nov 2023)	352	2.2
Rajasthan (Nov 2023)	307	1.8
Andhra Pradesh (May 2024)	273	1.7
Madhya Pradesh (Nov 2023)	234	1.6
Odisha (May 2024)	169	1.8
Haryana (Oct 2024)	137	1.1
Jharkhand (Nov-Dec 2024)	55	1.2

It has been rightly said that this is the 21st century and nothing we get is free of cost. We are often unable to see the hidden charges behind the vouchers and free items especially when it comes to political promises it is bound to have implications. Governments promise numerous of schemes on the eve of poll to get voters support but what is achievable and feasible are not clearly known to common people and they get swayed by it. A major amount of government's revenue comes from taxes (direct & indirect) and rest of the revenue from borrowings. These money funds important sectors like infrastructure development, healthcare, social security etc. But, due to illogical expenditure a large chunk of government's revenue is allocated to fulfill the pre poll promises which deteriorate financial health of government. If we talk about central government's expenditure, the fiscal deficit stood at 6.4% (actual) and 4.4% (budget estimates) for the year 2022-23 and 2024-25 [11].

Many states show same trends towards their fiscal management. Delhi government spent Rs. 4215 Crore (approximately 6% of the state's GDP) on freebies. Punjab took it to a step further and allocated Rs 20,000 crore to free electricity. If we talk about bigger states like Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra etc., they are not lagging. Madhya Pradesh being an agrarian state set aside a large amount of Rs. 18,984 crore (1.25% of budget) for freebies. And Maharashtra allocated a whopping amount of Rs. 46,000 Crore while Karnataka's freebie allocation stood at Rs. 60,000 crore [8]. Keeping in mind all the financial mess that could be done in the name of welfare, the visionary leader PM Atal Bihari Vajpayee in 2003 came up with the idea of capping fiscal deficit at an optimum

level. The Fiscal Deficit Budget Management Act (FRBM) 2003 recommends reducing fiscal deficit to 3% [12].

There is no such concrete evidence or researched facts that pre-poll promises win election or even affect the result of elections. But keeping aside its electoral aspects, it does have some impact on socio-economic terms. It is not certain that the so called freebie plays a bigger role in the election results. They may play a minor role but they can't tilt balance in favor of one party and yes if a party announces some lucrative scheme to the voters, other parties are also compelled to announce the same in competitive politics. It is seen that the promises worked wonder if there is a strong anti-incumbency i.e. if the incumbent government is not very popular. Considering the ground reality of financial assistance to women as freebie, it tells a different story. Taking recently concluded Jharkhand assembly election as an example. The incumbent JMM-led Hemant Soren government promised a direct transfer of Rs. 2500 per month to women of a particular age group [13]. And after gaining the thumping majority, the credit for which is given to the pre-poll promise of money in lieu of votes, the government is sending money in bank accounts of women. Now women are spending this money for their personal expenses and eventually contributing in economy by boosting the demand supply chain which can be termed as financial inclusion. The type of scheme used is not limited to Jharkhand only, but many states such as Maharashtra, Haryana, Karnataka, West Bengal etc. successively implemented this to lure voters [14].

Electoral freebies do have repercussions on society as a whole. Dependency theory is quite common to understand that the first time you give somebody something for free you are creating appreciation, the second time you create anticipation, likewise the third time it will be expectation. The fourth time if you give somebody something for free you are creating entitlement. Fifth time will result in dependency. As mentioned above, fiscal shortcoming is another aspect of pre-poll promises, as it has certain money value that is added to the preexisting government's budget ambit. Addition of this expenditure will ultimately be compensated by milking the taxpayers.

The pre-poll promises of financial assistant from successive governments have triggered gender biasedness, as in most of the cases financial aid that is given by different governments is women centric. It treats females as a weaker sex by offering few pennies every month. For example, Karnataka & Delhi government gives free ride to women in buses [15]. Women of different classes of society got benefitted by this but women whose family income are well off and can easily afford travelling expenditure are also enjoying free ride in the name of welfare. Males of poor class are deprived of these schemes compelling them to be gender insensitive.

Conclusion

In a nation where election is treated as a dance of festival, extravagant gifting of items to tempt votes and disregard the voters and poll in a whole is worrisome for the health of our democracy. The practice should be constituted as an evil practice and then as a corrupt practice through legal steps. The contents of manifesto help understanding the intent and can be useful in interpreting the reality of promises political parties have thrown towards the voters. It is seen that manifestos are released one or two days prior to the Election Day resulting in lack of time to thoroughly evaluate it which put voters in dilemma. After winning the election it is seen that the wave of pre-poll promises on which parties rides to power, suddenly make U-turn and do not pay any heed to implement it. Keeping this in mind, a special bench of judges should be constituted to review the implementation of promises made. Make manifesto a legally binding document on the parties to avoid impractical claims and in case of failing to do so, punishment clause such as banning from taking part in election should be inducted in it.

There is nothing wrong in making policies aimed at addressing the poor to bring this class in mainstream but in the name of welfare and to grab votes from them overriding the financial limit of government should not be allowed in any term. The onus to carry out free and fair elections in India is on election commission so it is necessary to grant the commission the power to enforce its guidelines on its own. Voters should cast their vote on the basis of performance and not on the false promises and propaganda after all it's the people of India that can bring change.

References

1. S. Subramaniam Balaji. *Tamil Nadu (2013) 9 SSC 659.*
2. *Fiscal Responsible and Budget Management (FRBM) Act, 2003.*
3. Tripathi, Suresh Mani (2016): "fundamental rights and Directive Principles of India", Anchor Academic Publishing.
4. Arun N. K (2013): *First define a freebie, Indian express.*
5. <https://www.eci.gov.in/election-manifestos/>
6. Kafliya Anand Ballabh (2007): *Democracy and Election Laws, Deep and Deep publication.*
7. Muley Satya (Oct 2022): *Understanding the freebie politics in India, financial express.*

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- II May - 2025

E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

Remarking An Analisation

8. <https://insideiim.com/current-affairs-for-mba-exam/freebies-in-indian-politics>.
9. Manoj C. G (2022): EC ask parties to explain how they plan to financial poll promises, Indian express. <https://www.eci.gov.in/election-manifestos/>
10. Sopariwala. Dorab R (2022): *The verdict decoding India's elections*, Yadav Brothers.
11. Kaushik Sudhanshu (2023): *The future is ours, the political promise of India's youth*, Harper Collins publication.
12. <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/editorial/sops-for-votes-the-hindu-editorial-on-election-promises/article65822617.ece>
13. Naurin Elin (2011): *Election Promises, Party Behaviour and Voter Perceptions*, Springer.
14. Ali Zaheer (2020): *Communities as vote bank*, Akar Books Publication.
15. Swargiary Khritish (2025): *THE POLITICS OF FREEBIES: electoral promises and their impact on Indian democracy*, Scholars press.